

SOCIAL SCIENCES

EPIGRAPHIC MONUMENTS OF THE CITY BAKU SETTLEMENT MASHTAGI

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Abstract

The archaeological monuments of Mashtaga dating from the 9th to the 19th centuries, particularly epigraphic monuments and tombstones, are of special interest. Many of these artifacts bear inscriptions in Arabic script, which provide significant historical information.

Mashtaga is considered one of the key architectural centers of Absheron. The abundance of mosques, bath complexes, fortification structures, residential and public buildings strongly supports this view. It is no coincidence that the renowned architectural historian S.S. Fatullayev noted that after the city of Baku, Mashtaga was ranked second place in terms of architectural richness, especially highlighting its numerous mosques, bathhouses, and public buildings dating back to the medieval period.

It should be noted that these buildings are not only architectural monuments. They also reflect the socio-economic life, artistic expressions, trade relations, and political environment of the region during various historical periods. Therefore, the inscriptions on these monuments possess exceptional significance for historical research.

Keywords: Absheron, grave monuments, vault, castle, archaeological excavations.

One can consider the settlement of Mashtaga as one of the major centers of Absheron's most significant architectural monuments. The numerous mosques, bathhouse complexes, defensive structures, water reservoirs (ovdans), public and residential buildings found here fully justify such a characterization [2, 7].

It is no coincidence that art historian and prominent researcher of Azerbaijani architectural history, architect Sh.S. Fatullayev (Figarov), specifically emphasized that "in terms of the richness of historically constructed public buildings, Mashtaga ranks second in Absheron after the city of Baku, and the dense concentration of numerous mosques, bathhouses, and ovdans is an exceptional phenomenon for the Absheron region" [9, 18].

An inscription on the portal of a mosque built in Mashtaga at the beginning of the 15th century is composed of four lines in Arabic.

Translation: "Mosques belong to Allah. Do not call upon anyone besides Allah. O Muhammad, this blessed mosque was built by Bira Arghutay ibn Adam ibn Haji Khalil in the year 817 AH (1415 AD), during the reign of Shirvanshah Sultan Ibrahim" [4, 92].

The "Sayyids" cemetery is located in the western part of the settlement. It was named "Sayyids" because a high-ranking sayyid, who once lived in the neighborhood known as "Sayyids" in Mashtaga, was buried there, and a mausoleum was erected over his grave.

The wide area surrounding the mausoleum was enclosed on all sides by low walls. In subsequent years, the graves and crypts of this sayyid's relatives and other sayyids who had lived in the area were also placed within this cemetery.

The mausoleum of Aghalbaba, which is the main subject of this study, is located on the western side of the "Sayyids" cemetery and was built from limestone. The square-plan structure has exterior dimensions of 5.25 × 5.25 meters. The mausoleum is cubical in form, with a body and dome cover. The grave of the mausoleum's occupant, measuring 1.70 × 0.80 × 0.65 m, is

located inside, near the southern wall. The entrance, featuring a pointed arch, is positioned within a portal on the eastern façade. Above the door, there is a two-line inscription measuring 0.80 × 0.45 m. The inscription is carved in a mixed Arabic-Persian script (Figure 2):

"This new grave belongs to Seyid Kamil, son of Seyid Mirza Rahim, leader of the wise (gnostics). It was built by Seyid Shahmirza and Seyid Hamza, from among the Sayyids, in the month of Rabi al-Thani, year 1103 AH (1692 AD)" (Figure 1).

From the reading and translation of the inscription, it is understood that the mausoleum was built by Seyid Shahmirza and Seyid Hamza in 1103 AH (1692 AD) over the grave of Seyid Kamil, son of Seyid Mirza Rahim.

According to epigraphist scholar Sima Kerimzadeh, several flaws can be observed in the inscription. Firstly, the script is primitive and does not conform to any specific calligraphic style, suggesting that the engraver was likely a novice calligrapher. Secondly, although there was space to insert diacritical marks for certain letters, the calligrapher neglected to do so. Thirdly, unnecessary diacritical marks were placed above and below some letters, potentially leading to misreading many words in the inscription.

The inscription of the mausoleum, known as "Aghalbaba" (or "Agha-Ali-baba"), was first published by M.S. Nematova in 1963, but the reading and translation included numerous errors [6, 154]. For example, in the first line of the inscription, the word "ننر" (na'ir) was misread with an added letter (1) that does not exist in the original, and this insertion was made without any notation. The words in this line were read incorrectly according to the rules of Arabic grammar. The second line of the inscription was read completely inaccurately and with foreign elements. For instance: ...

Moreover, the date of construction was mistakenly recorded with a 28-year discrepancy—being read as 1131 AH instead of the correct 1103 AH [6, 154].

Traces of a smaller inscription remain on the left side of the façade wall. Due to the fragmentary state, it is unreadable. It is assumed that this inscription contained the name of the master builder [7, 106–110].

At present, a small structure adjoining the northern wall of the mausoleum draws attention. Within this structure, stone-built hearths and chimneys are still visible. According to local accounts, pilgrims who once visited the mausoleum used to cook votive meals in the hearth of this simple annex.

One of Mashtaga's ancient monuments is the historic "Friday" Mosque located in the "Khunhar" neighborhood. The "Khunhar neighborhood" is one of the oldest residential areas in Mashtaga, dating back to the Middle Ages. According to local elders, the area acquired its name because of the valor of the warriors who lived there and the considerable bloodshed that occurred, hence it was called "Khunhar." In Persian, "Khunhar" means "bloodthirsty" or "blood-shedder."

Another tradition holds that the "Khunhar" neighborhood was the site where "sinners," condemned to punishment, were executed in various ways. During excavations in a courtyard on C. Jabbarli Street, human skeletal remains were found together with domestic artifacts, lending credence to this narrative. There is also the theory that "Khunhar" derives from "Hunhar" (the Huns), an ancient Turkic tribe. It is plausible that the phrase "blood-drinkers" referred to fierce Turkic soldiers who, like the Mongols, quenched their thirst with the horse's blood—so the Persian-speaking Tats or Shahsevan called them "khunxor."

In the Middle Ages, Mashtaga contained several neighborhoods besides "Khunhar," each with its own mosque. Notably, the central "Mashtaga Friday Mosque," which served as the main congregational mosque, has been active since the medieval period and continues to function today.

It is likely that many residents of medieval Mashtaga spoke the local "Tat dialect," which evolved from Persian over centuries, and that the dominant language in "Khunhar" was that dialect, confirming the Persian (Tat) origin of its name.

The "Khunhar" mosque in central Mashtaga is a rectangular structure with a dome supported by eight columns at the center of the prayer hall. The facade is framed by four circular columns. Inside the eastern wall—at an area called the "takhcha"—are reliefs of various geometric forms carved in stone, crafted by the master architect with aesthetic finesse. The stone panel above the entrance portal features two Arabic inscriptions in Nasta'liq script—each a couplet—of which the translation is:

1. "By the command to obey Allah, this mosque was established. Only one who believes in Allah till the Last Day can enliven God's mosque."

2. "The construction and minor repairs of this holy mosque were carried out by the residents of the 'Khunhar' neighborhood in Hijri 1229 (1813/14 AD)."

Another stone panel measuring 0.42 × 0.30 m, placed outside between windows, also in Arabic Nasta'liq, reads:

1. "Novruz Mashgatali."
2. "Məşədiqulu bin Seyid Rza."

This panel credits two master builders—including Novruz Mashqatali and Məşədiqulu, son of Seyid Rza—and confirms that the mosque was renovated by neighborhood residents in Hijri 1229 (1813–14), but historical study by Ə. Ələsgərzadə and M. Nəmət suggests the mosque predates that date considerably. Recent restoration works uncovered two wells intended for water supply and numerous ceramic fragments—both glazed and unglazed—for domestic and farm use. Inside one of the wells, two inscribed stone panels and a carved phallic-shaped "alem" (finial) from the dome were discovered. The inscriptions include parts of the "Kalima-i-shahada"—on one panel "Aliyyan Waliyyullah," and on another "Lā ilāha illāh Muḥammadun Rasūlallah." Six of these stones remain inside the well. During the Soviet era, especially in the 1920s–30s, mosques and shrines were destroyed, causing irreparable cultural damage. It is believed that the inscriptions from the Khunhar mosque were removed during the purges and thrown into the well, subsequently sealed with soil.

Interestingly, like the Mashtaga Friday Mosque, the Khunhar mosque's courtyard also has an underground passage leading from an internal water well. Archeological artifacts suggest the Khunhar mosque was part of the 17th-century Mashtaga palace complex on the Absheron Peninsula—this complex included Khunhar Mosque, the Mashtaga Friday Mosque, the area known today as "Agha meydani," a small palace, and was surrounded by fortress walls.

Earthquakes over time damaged many homes and historic monuments in Mashtaga. Based on I. N. Berezin's findings, after the 1761 earthquake the Khunhar neighborhood mosque was ruined but thoroughly restored in 1813–14. A devastating earthquake in late December 1841 again destroyed the mosque. Finally, it was reconstructed for the third time in 1875, and during that restoration a poorly executed Naskh-style Nasta'liq Arabic inscription was added above the facade portal, stating:

1. "By Allah's will this mosque was repaired."

2. "In Sha'ban 1292 AH (2 September – 1 October 1875)."

Another inscription reads:

1. "This mosque was repaired by the All-Powerful Allah."

2. "In Ramazan 1292 AH (1–30 October 1875)."

Locals sometimes refer to the Khunhar neighborhood mosque as the "Akhund Sheikh Huseyn Mosque." Akhund Sheikh Huseyn Kabala Abdulhamid oglu, who studied in Karbala and Najaf from age 16 for 25 years and earned the title "Sheikh," returned to Mashtaga in 1922. He first served as a cleric at Akhund Mehammad Nabi's, then at the Khunhar (Old Friday) Mosque. Under his leadership, minor repairs were made in 1929, but in the 1930s the mosque was closed during repressions; Sheikh Huseyn was arrested several times and later released.

The mosque once had a tall minaret and dome in the Eastern architectural style, but these were destroyed during Soviet purges in the 1930s. In the 1940s, the façade and its four supporting columns were rebuilt by

architects Kəblə Heybatqulu oğlu and Aqaqulu. Following Azerbaijan's independence in the 1990s, thanks to philanthropist Haji Zakir's tireless efforts, major restoration was carried out based on his architectural plan, including the reconstruction of the minaret and both domes. Today the minaret stands 23 m tall with a diameter of 3 m 5 cm, and the large dome measures 2 m 70 cm in diameter.

Finally, the Haji Kərbalayi Hüseyn Mosque is located in the "Dərə" neighborhood of Mashtaga on Mammadyarov Street. Information about its construction was obtained from two stone inscriptions on-site.

On the entrance gate of the mosque, a two-line inscription in Arabic, written in *Naskh* script, has been preserved. The size of the inscription is **1.0 x 0.49 m** and it has been read as follows:

1. "In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful. The one who believes in mosques is like a fish in water."
2. "The sons of Karbalayi Safar – Haji Karbalayi Hüseyn and Isgandar, and Karbalayi Lutfully, son of Hajiverdi. Year 1291 AH (1874/75 AD)."

Another inscription is preserved on the right side of the mosque entrance. Its content is as follows:

1. "Master Murtuzagulu and master Agamali Mashqetali. Both are scribes. (Note: Researcher M. Nemat has indicated that this mosque was built by Rustam Kurdakhani)" (8, p.105).

Haji Karbalayi Hüseyn, who lived in Mashtaga, was the father of Haji Gani, Haji Khaliq, Haji Gadir, and Haji Agadash. During the Soviet era, this mosque was subjected to repression, and for years, worship was prohibited there. The mosque building was used as a shop (since 1991). After Azerbaijan regained its political independence, the mosque was restored by local elders and religious believers and is currently operational.

One of the mosques built in Mashtaga in the 19th century is the "Govhara" or "Govharbika" mosque. It is one of the lesser-studied mosques. A stone inscription measuring **1.05 x 0.35 m** is preserved at the entrance of the mosque. This inscription provides certain information about the mosque. It reads:

"In the name of Allah, the Most Merciful and Compassionate.

Quran, Surah IX, verse 18.

The foundation of this mosque was laid by Mr. Haji Mahammad, son of Rza Bey."

Year 1131 AH (1893/94 AD).

From this inscription, we learn who commissioned the mosque, but no information is provided about the architect (8, p.110).

In the vicinity of **Secondary School No. 187**, the religious site once hosted sermons by **Akhund Mirza Hüseyn**. During the Soviet era, the mosque remained unused, but restoration and repair work is currently ongoing (Figure 5).

A particularly interesting structure is located in the gardens in the northern part of **Mashtaga village**, referred to by locals as the "**Kokburma Pir**". The building is made of finely cut limestone and has a rectangular interior and exterior layout. Its front side faces east. The construction date of the tomb is not indicated, but

some **gravestone fragments** inside the tomb allow for a tentative estimation.

One fragment includes a portion of **verse 256 from the Quran**. Another gravestone fragment reads:

"This grave belongs to the late, forgiven..."

However, the name of the deceased is missing.

On a third gravestone fragment, the following words are legible:

"This grave belongs to the late Pir..., son of Ali -- -"

The headstones are damaged and worn, making the inscriptions largely illegible. It is likely that the place and building are still called a "**pir**" by locals due to the person commemorated by the headstone. One fragment contains the **Hijri year 1055 (1645/46 AD)**, suggesting that the tomb was built in the **first half of the 17th century** (6, p.92).

Among the **historical architectural monuments** of the Absheron Peninsula dating to the Middle Ages, **defensive structures** also hold significant importance. These include fortified castles and palace-type residences.

The castles of Absheron (Mardakan, Nardaran, Ramana, Bilgah, etc.) were part of a **unified defense system**, serving as shelters and watch posts. There were also defensive structures in the **Mashtaga region**.

The **defensive castles** on the Absheron Peninsula mostly date to the **13th–14th centuries**. These castles surrounded the peninsula from the northeast, north, and partially the south, forming the frontline of the defense system. They also served as reliable shelters for local rulers to protect themselves from each other. The location of these castles along the **northeastern coast** indicates that danger was expected from that direction.

If the enemy seized one of the coastal castles, they would encounter serious resistance from the inland defensive structures in **Mashtaga, Zabrat, Gala, and Ramana**.

According to historical records, **approaching attacks** were signaled by **bonfires at night and smoke during the day**. News of an enemy attack was passed **from castle to castle**, mobilizing the entire Absheron population. If the smoke signal started from the northern coast, it would then pass through **Nardaran, Mashtaga, and Ramana**, eventually reaching **Keshlə** and finally **Baku**, the last point of the unified defense system. A close look at the **map of Absheron** shows the continuity of connections between the **coastal defense structures** and the **inland areas**.

According to researchers, **there were over 30 such defensive structures** on the Absheron Peninsula. Some have survived to this day, while others have collapsed or disappeared due to various reasons. The discovered **archaeological monuments** provide grounds to suggest the existence of the "**Mashtaga Palace Complex**", characteristic of Absheron.

This complex included the "**Khunkhar**" mosque, the "**Juma**" mosque, an area known today among locals as "**Agha Square**", and the "**Khan's Palace**" located there. The palace complex was entirely surrounded by **castle walls**, the remains of which were destroyed by a **powerful earthquake in December 1841**. Some fragments of the walls survived into the **early**

20th century. Researchers **I.P. Shcheblikin** and **Y.V. Pakhomov** photographed the ruins in **1926**.

In his work "*Gulistan-i Iram*", **A. Bakikhanov** mentioned that **Mirza Mahammad Khan II** built a new castle for himself in Mashtaga. However, researchers **Shcheblikin** and **Pakhomov** noted that **fortified walls existed in Mashtaga long before the construction of that castle**. During their research, they discovered **stone fragments with inscriptions**, though it was not clear which part of the structure they belonged to.

On one of the stone fragments, **Y.V. Pakhomov** read:

"Building... for Mahammad Ibrahim Ali oglu... in the eighth year..."

However, a complete and clear understanding could not be achieved.

From the **historical documents related to Mashtaga**, and based on the research by **Pakhomov** and **Shcheblikin**, it becomes evident that as early as the **17th century**, a **castle complex typical of Absheron** existed here. Fragments of the **castle, gardens, mansions, and water reservoirs** are still present today.

The **German traveler and physician I.Y. Lerch**, who visited the areas occupied by the Russians between **1723 and 1735**, stayed at **Dargahqulu Khan's house** in Mashtaga in **1733** and documented his experiences:

"On July 27, 1733, we arrived at Meshketa, the best village around Baku. There lived Dargah Sultan, a tall, handsome, and brave warrior. His house was large and beautiful. The building, decorated with various patterns inside and outside, had two stone pools in its yard. He hosted us in Eastern style and had about 50 different dishes laid on the table. There were many large buildings around the area." [2, p.101]

On the Mashtaga territory, the second garden pavilion built by Khan Dargahqulu was located on the left side of the Mashtaga-Nardaran road, in the area known among residents as the "Khan's Garden." This was a two-story, large building whose remnants remained visible until recently, but its site was later occupied by the buildings of Psychiatric Hospital No. 3. **A. Bakikhanov's father—Mirza Mahammad Khan II**—also lived for some time in this residence. **Mirza Mahammad Khan II** ruled the Khanate in Baku between 1784 and 1791 but, having lost a power struggle, had to retreat to Quba. At the end of the 19th century, he divided the territory of the Baku Khanate with **Huseyngulu Khan** and chose Mashtaga for his own residence. He constructed a new fortress there for defense purposes, but soon had to return to Quba again. Research by **I. P. Shcheblikin** and **Y. V. Pakhomov** on the Mashtaga fortress shows that the fortress built by **Mirza Mahammad Khan II** had round towers at its corners (similar to those built in the Nardaran fortress in 1301 AH/M 1883-84).

According to one of Mashtaga village's elder residents, **Seyid Rasul**, there were underground passages from the fortress to surrounding areas. Both the fortress and the Khan's palace were destroyed by frequent earthquakes in the region.

In recent years, excavations have uncovered the remaining walls of the fortress. It is hoped that in the future, comprehensive archaeological studies will take

place in Mashtaga and the mentioned area, allowing for a detailed investigation of the settlement's history and ancient monuments.

It is known that the Absheron Peninsula has a relatively arid climate. In other words, it might initially appear to be a "waterless land." But closer examination reveals that historically—and even in the modern period—agriculture and horticulture had reached a certain level of development there. Travelers who visited the peninsula spoke with interest about the greenery, orchards, and cultivated gardens they saw.

According to **Abdurrashid Bakuvi's** records, figs, grapes, and pomegranates were cultivated in the outskirts of Baku. Archaeological excavations also confirm that fruit and vegetable crops, as well as industrial plants, were grown in and around Baku in medieval times. There is also evidence that cotton was cultivated on the Absheron Peninsula.

This raises the question: how did the local population meet the water needs of these agricultural lands? The answer is simple: through numerous wells and cisterns! Yes, wells and cisterns played an exceptional role in the water supply of Absheron villages. These cisterns are widespread on the peninsula and in Gobustan.

Studying the cisterns provides insight into medieval Absheron material culture, overall water-supply systems, and architectural characteristics. In the dry subtropical climate of the Absheron Peninsula, the quantity and distinctive features of these cisterns are striking. Researchers **V. I. Tochilov**, **S. A. Dadashev**, **M. A. Huseynov**, **S. Bronevsky**, **I. P. Shcheblikin**, **E. A. Gasimov**, and others have written about them. **E. A. Gasimov's** monograph "*Water-Supply Systems of Medieval Cities of Azerbaijan*" explores in depth how water-supply systems played a decisive role in the development of urban everyday life, economy, and crafts.

One of the cisterns still existing in Mashtaga stands beside the road leading to the Bilgah gardens. Locally, it is called the "Amiraslan cistern." Presently entirely neglected, this cistern in the garden is intact and still usable, though its abandonment and neglect pose a risk. One can descend to the bottom via steps on the side. Its top is constructed in arched form. In modern times, taking water systems as "adequate," abandoning such a monument is unjustifiable (Figure 6).

On the cistern's entrance, there are three small Arabic inscriptions, each consisting of two lines. The first inscription reads:

"Allah, Muhammad, Ali
Fatima, Hasan, Husayn"

The second inscription reads:

"Built by Haji Qulu.

Construction date 1311 AH (1893)."

The third inscription reads:

"Endowment of Haji Rustam and Meshadi Amir Aslan" (8, p.109).

In 2023, during excavations at the "Seyids' Cemetery" west of Mashtaga, a three-stepped stone sarcophagus-tomb was discovered one meter deep in the ground. The sarcophagus's right and left sides are made in four-step style, with a slightly pitched upper surface that angles toward the center. The Arabic inscription begins on the right and ends on the left. The last word

on the headstone, written in Kufic script, is “Allah.” On the sarcophagus, again in Kufic, it indicates that it belongs to Abdullah ibn Malikah. Additionally, verse 255 of Sura Al-Baqarah (“Ayat al-Kursi”) from the Qur’an is inscribed. This verse is noted as “one of the prayers most clearly expressing the unity of faith toward the Lord.” Sun-ornament motifs and the words “Ya Ali” appear on the sarcophagus’s four-step base. Based on its design and Kufic script, the tomb dates to the 9th–10th centuries.

I. In the “Pirsaid” Cemetery in northeast Mashtaga, three crypts have been recorded. Each crypt contains a stone tablet naming the interred.

First crypt – the rectangular tablet reads:

“This is the late Sheikhalı Badkubi, son of the late Agadadash, 1329 AH” (1911–12 AD).

To improve visibility, the stone’s surface was whitened and the inscriptions painted black, with a black-framed border. In its lower-right corner is depicted a six-petaled flower.

Second crypt – its arch-shaped door tablet states:

“The late Qasim, son of the late Haji Karim, died on 12 Muharram al-haram, 1334 AH” (1915–16 AD). The tablet features two-row inscriptions and ornamented arch border in reddish stone.

Third crypt – the tablet reads:

“This is the late Abdullah, son of Nabi. 9 Safar al-muzaffar, 1334 AH (1915–16 AD).”

The facades of the second and third crypts are arched with two courses. The reddish stone tablets are edged with raised borders. The texts are executed in raised script, split into two parts; the entrances are arched. Around the inscriptions are simple geometric patterns. Nearby are other tomb monuments in sarcophagus and headstone form.

1. **Rectangular headstone**, partially buried. Its side carvings include framed inscriptions, and eight-petaled floral motifs in rectangular panels above. Because partly buried, the date could not be determined.

2. A **trapezoidal sarcophagus** appears stepped at first glance. The top surface usually contained the inscription; its sides are decorated with geometric, floral, and architectural motifs: lower two rows of ornamental floral branches (2–3 petals), central wide band with eight-petaled floral and geometric network, upper two rows with vertical lines. The upper border is eroded, so inscriptions or ornaments there could not be identified. At the foot of the sarcophagus there is a space for lighting candles—a tradition linked to ancient beliefs, and some researchers associate it with “a symbolic meaning borne of belief in the hereafter.” According to elders, until the 1940s the sarcophagus stood inside an ancient shrine which was later destroyed. Women without children and those seeking protection would visit the shrine. On top of the sarcophagus are two stones—one tall and elongated, shaped like a cap—stones commonly placed on the graves of Sufi sheikhs. It is therefore likely that the person buried there was a spiritual figure, a scholar, or a saint. Based on comparison with similar monuments, the sarcophagus dates to the 16th–17th centuries.

II. In the “Seyids” Cemetery of Mashtaga settlement, these grave monuments were recorded:

1. A capstone with a pitched top and bordered inscription in two parts; the main text is inside panels. The date is 1191 AH (1777–78 AD).

2. A sarcophagus-style headstone whose top edge has a frame; the sarcophagus is rectangular with zigzag lines etched on a narrow frame. The date is inscribed as 1172 AH (1758–59 AD).

The sarcophagi and headstones in the Mashtaga cemetery date broadly from the 9th to the 19th centuries. The crypts date to the early 20th century.

Azerbaijan’s gravestone and sarcophagus monuments from the 9th–19th centuries are richly decorated with geometric and floral motifs and images, and feature inscriptions in various Arabic scripts. Unfortunately, unlike with other architectural monuments, inscriptions rarely include the names of the skilled craftsmen who produced these enduring works of art [2, 8; 1, 242–244].

Figure 1. Stone inscription on the door of the Ağal-Bəbə shrine

Figure 2. General view of Maštağa Xunxar Friday Mosque

Figure 3. Stone inscriptions discovered inside the water well located in the courtyard of the "Khunkhar" Friday Neighborhood Mosque in Mashtaga (17th–18th centuries).

Figure 4. Haji Karbalayi Huseyn Neighborhood Mosque (19th century)

Figure 5. "Govhar Bike" Neighborhood Mosque (19th century)

Figure 6. Meshadi Emiraslan Ovdan in the Quriney Gardens of Mashtaga (19th century)

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